

PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATIONAL INNOVATIONS: FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING

Begnazarova Zebinisobegim Dilshod kizi

A Student of Karshi Economics And Pedagogy University

Abstract: The most effective second/foreign language acquisition methods for children, US, Japanese and Singapore experience. Also, practical methods that help the child feel safe and protected and learn a second language outside of school in a completely natural way, like acquiring his mother tongue, effectively teach foreign languages to children through online and traditional lessons. teaching methods.

Keywords: foreign language, online education, platform, YouTube, 3D flashcard, John Locke, strategy.

Children's developing young minds naturally learn new languages 87% faster than middle-aged adults. Learning a second language broadens our worldview, exposes us to other cultures, and serves as a valuable tool in our personal and professional development. Parents, like the school, are crucial in this process. "The soul of a newborn baby is like a ball of clean cotton." What to write in the child's soul in the style of "top-clean cotton," in his opinion, is entirely up to the adults.

"As a result, how a child develops into a person, that is, what personal qualities are found in him, depends on the experience he gets from life, the life concepts and ideas he gets in the process of communicating with others," according to English scientist John Locke. Providing stimulating, engaging environments and activities for children to learn new words can assist them in achieving the cognitive gains made in the early stages of learning. Using a few simple methods to develop a second language (foreign language) in the home environment of children up to 8 years old will result in 63% successful acquisition of another language from the child's first age.

Methods that can be used on children as young as eight years old: Play is the universal language of children and is essential for learning new words and phrases. Children learn about the world around them on their own at a young age, through everyday activities. However, their favorite pastime - play - is one of the best and most effective forms of learning. Play assists children in developing their listening abilities, following directions, vocabulary, and social skills.

When teaching new words to children under the age of four, it is recommended that parents create small stories by memorizing new words during daily activities, such as dressing children, preparing food, or bathing the child; at this age, the child's main focus is not on learning something, but on action games; the ability of a child to memorize new words in a short period of time, through imagery, was tested in scientists' "K-Okila" experiment.

Mini-libraries for teachers, parents, and specialists, art-vibe drawing books for children under four years old to learn their native language and a foreign language as a second language with great interest. The use of lego and 3D size toys will cause the child to listen carefully to information for up to 40 minutes without becoming bored. Place pictures in their native language and the second language in places where children's eyes frequently fall, such as the refrigerator, TV, bath, room

Doors, tables, and chairs, and repeat them together to see the active words that the child uses in their vocabulary. Serves to increase. Parents should constantly prepare worksheets for their children to paint, draw, and search for words, enter daily news, and draw together new models of the heroes of fairy tales or cartoon characters they have read, and name the new model prepared in English. The compilation of simple and small stories in the language will cause the child to broaden his worldview.

Coloring helps toddlers develop fine motor skills, which will be useful when it comes time to learn to write. Additionally, learning the foreign language names of things they see frequently and labeling them is a great way to help them memorize new words in the target language. Using 3D cards to teach new vocabulary. While repetitive vocabulary exercises are important for learning new words and phrases, the problem with them is that children can quickly become bored with them. It is recommended that small melodious songs be created twice a day, once during breakfast and once after dinner, using flashcards and 3D cards for the day and new words. Traveling abroad with children (to a country where the language you are teaching is spoken) is also the most effective way to learn a language. However, if funds are limited for such trips, eating at a restaurant serving traditional dishes or visiting museum exhibits displaying cultures from around the world will provide an environment in which children can learn a new foreign language.

Today, we have several techniques for learning foreign languages and various methods for teaching a foreign language, but they all have something in common. That is, if you ask how to learn a second/foreign language, the answer is the same in each of these approaches: use the language regularly. The key to successfully learning any foreign language is exposure and use. When it comes to teaching a foreign language in primary school, it is clear that the number of lessons is insufficient; that is, if the child does not have contact with the foreign language he is learning after school, everything he has learned will quickly fade. This is true for all school subjects, not just foreign languages. Children should be encouraged to use the words they learn outside of class as much as possible, because using a language is the best way to learn it. Of course, teachers and parents play an important role in this.

First and foremost, the goal of teaching a foreign language is to encourage the child rather than to force him. Children learn through play at a young age in a stress-free and pressure-free environment. As a result, it is necessary to create a stimulating and supportive environment for learning a foreign language. How do you create a stimulating environment for language learning? A child must feel safe and protected to learn a second language outside of school in the same natural way he learns his mother tongue. We should praise and reward the child for everything he does correctly. If they face difficulties, it is critical that they receive support and work together to overcome them. Allow the child to rest and engage in other activities if he appears tired; learning a foreign language outside of the classroom should take the form of more active games rather than formal education.

British scientists proved conclusively in 1986 that learning foreign languages at a young age yields the best results. When learning their mother tongue, young children use their innate, instinctive language acquisition strategies, so they learn their language from a young age, without any grammar, through the words they hear. The younger the child, the more he or she relies on innate strategies to learn foreign languages. Rather, as children get older and their effective innate learning strategies give way to other forms of learning, they learn foreign languages in the same way they learn other school subjects. They begin learning languages by memorizing words and grammar rules, and as a result, the language in question is now different from the child's natural learning stage. When a child begins learning a second language is one of the best indicators of his or her fluency. Children who

begin learning a foreign language later often learn the rules of grammar without difficulty, but they always differ from children who begin learning it at a young age in one aspect: there are a number of pronunciation issues. Children who naturally acquire a second language at a young age often have better pronunciation and a better sense of language than their peers who begin learning the same language at a later age, so the language simply becomes part of their natural environment, and as a result, they learn other languages easily and quickly later in life. Children in the United States, Japan, and Singapore learned the language at a very young age simply by watching cartoons, and only after they had a developed sense of the language did they begin to learn the rules of grammar. Singing songs in a foreign language - children love songs, and the melody helps them remember some words, so songs are a great memorization and learning technique. Singing songs in their native language is a great and effective way to help children learn a foreign language. For example, finding and singing along to children's songs on YouTube can help improve pronunciation. Incorporating a foreign language into your daily activities - because children absorb everything like sponges in early childhood, it is critical to share correct and reliable knowledge with them. Through the game, the child unconsciously strengthens the mother tongue in addition to the foreign language. Learning a foreign language online is not only enjoyable and, in many cases, free, but it is also the best way to improve your language skills. The advantage of learning a foreign language online is that it fits perfectly into the lifestyle of children: lessons are short and include tests, and children can take these tests anywhere on their phones, in between other activities. Online educational sites and apps are full of fun and creative activities for kids that keep children's attention much longer than traditional lessons.

REFERENCES LIST:

1. Easy Ways to Teach Your Child a Foreign Language From 0-8 Years <https://www.theculturedkid.com/blog/nurture-language-development>
2. Foreign language teaching methods to help children speak fluently | Allison Academy <https://www.allisonacademy.com/parents/parenting/foreign-language-teaching-methods/>
3. Marufova, Z. (2022). LINGUISTIC AND CULTURAL MEANS OF REALIZING THE CONCEPT OF "BEAUTY" IN CLASSIC ARTISTIC TEXTS. *International Journal Of Literature And Languages*, 2(10), 05-13.
4. Bilingual Babes: Teach Your Child A Second Language <https://www.parents.com/toddlerspreschoolers/development/language/bilingual-babes-teach-your-child-a-second-language/>
5. Nabievna, M. Z. (2021). LINGUISTIC INTERPRETATION OF THE CONCEPT OF "BEAUTY" AND THE EXPRESSION OF GENDER ETHALON IN IT. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(12), 100-103.
6. How to Teach Your Children a Second Language <https://www.wikihow.com/Teach-Your-Children-a-Second-Language?amp=1>
7. What's the best way to teach children a second language? New research produces surprising results <https://theconversation.com/amp/whats-the-best-way-to-teach-children-a-second-language-new-research-produces-surprising-results-122059>

